

Optimizing Uganda's Electrification Strategy: Insights from GEP & OnSSET Modeling

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Abbreviations

AFDB – African Development Bank
ERA – Electricity Regulatory Authority
ESMAP – Energy Sector Management Assistance Program
GEP – Global Electrification Platform
GIS – Geographic Information System
IEA – International Energy Agency
IPPs – Independent Power Producers
IRENA – International Renewable Energy Agency
MEMD – Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development
MV – Medium Voltage
OnSSET – Open Source Spatial Electrification Tool
PV – Photovoltaic
QGIS – Quantum Geographic Information System
REA – Rural Electrification Agency
SHS – Solar Home Systems
UBOS – Uganda Bureau of Statistics
UEDCL – Uganda Electricity Distribution Company Limited
UEGCL – Uganda Electricity Generation Company Limited
UETCL – Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited

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Executive Summary

This report presents key highlights from the OnSSET training conducted from April 28 to May 9, 2025, with a primary focus on modeling electrification scenarios for Uganda. The training involved sourcing raw geospatial and demographic data, cleaning and reprojecting it into a consistent GIS format, calibrating the dataset, and applying Python-based modeling to simulate electrification outcomes aligned with national targets.

The scenarios were designed around Uganda's policy priorities as set out in Vision 2040 and the Uganda Energy Policy 2023. Two main scenarios were analyzed:

- Scenario 1 – Ideal Grid Expansion: Achieving 100% electrification by 2040 through comprehensive grid rollout.
- Scenario 2 – Off-grid Focus: Achieving 100% electrification by 2040 using a cost-effective, off-grid-led approach with limited grid expansion.

Each scenario incorporated demographic assumptions for 2040, including a population of 61 million, 60% urbanization, an average rural household size of 5, and urban household size of 4. The results were visualized in QGIS and tested under multiple configurations, including variations in the priority given to grid intensification. Modeling results demonstrate that the off-grid scenario (Scenario 2) reduces total investment by \$400million compared to full grid expansion, while electrifying 51.7% of new connections via solar home systems (SHS). This approach aligns with Uganda's fiscal constraints and accelerates access for remote populations. Scenario 2 offers several strategic advantages:

- Aligns with current fiscal constraints while still meeting electrification goals.
- Accelerates energy access through decentralized, off-grid solutions driven by private sector participation.
- Enables smarter grid investments through targeted extension and intensification where most impactful.
- Mobilizes private capital through partnerships with off-grid service providers and investors.

Based on these findings, Uganda should strongly consider adopting the off-grid scenario as the foundation for its national electrification strategy.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Background: Uganda electricity sector

Uganda's electricity sector is governed by the Electricity Act of 1999 and guided by key national policies, including the *National Vision 2040* and the *Energy Policy of 2023*, which set an ambitious target of achieving 100% electricity access by 2040.

The sector is overseen by several key institutions:

- Ministry of Energy and Mineral Development (MEMD): Responsible for policy formulation and sector budgeting.
- Electricity Regulatory Authority (ERA): An independent regulator that sets tariffs, issues licenses (e.g. for Independent Power Producers - IPPs), and develops regulations and guidelines for the sector.
- Uganda Electricity Generation Company Limited (UEGCL): Oversees the development and management of government-owned power plants.
- Uganda Electricity Transmission Company Limited (UETCL): Manages the national transmission infrastructure (above 33kV).
- Uganda Electricity Distribution Company Limited (UEDCL): Oversees the distribution infrastructure below 33kV and leads grid extension efforts. There is one private Utility – WENRECO which manages a remote region recently connected to the main grid.
- Independent Power Producers (IPPs): Operate various hydro and solar generation plants.
- Mini-grid Developers: Develop and manage isolated or grid-connected mini-grids with licensing and oversight from ERA and MEMD.
- Solar Home Systems (SHS) Providers: Operate on a self-regulated basis, primarily through industry associations.

Despite major investments over the past two decades in generation, grid expansion, and electrification programs—including subsidies for connection costs and public awareness campaigns—significant challenges remain:

- Only 50% of generated electricity is currently consumed, with households accounting for 22% and commercial/industrial users for 78%.
- The average distance of settlements from the medium-voltage grid is approximately 3.7 km.
- Grid connection rates remain low due to factors such as:
 - High upfront connection costs;
 - Limited financial capacity of service providers/utilities to pre-finance and stock materials;
 - High internal wiring costs for households;
 - Dispersed rural populations;
 - Oversupply of power leading to payments for deemed energy and elevated tariffs.

To address these challenges, the government is committed to achieving universal electrification by 2040, leveraging a mix of grid and off-grid solutions as outlined in its long-term national and energy policies.

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This report evaluates Uganda's electrification strategy by assessing different pathways to achieve universal electricity access by 2040. It leverages the OnSSET model to explore cost-effective solutions while addressing financial constraints, infrastructure limitations, and settlement distribution. The report further presents a set of two electrification scenarios simulated during the EMP-A 2025 OnSSET training. The focus is on spatial least-cost modeling to inform national policy decisions and identify the most appropriate electrification technologies by location.

1.2 Objective and aims

The main objective is to determine the most effective approach to achieving national electrification targets with the specific objectives as;

- Simulate and evaluate electrification pathways to meet 100% access by 2040.
- Compare least-cost scenarios incorporating grid and off-grid solutions.
- Develop spatially referenced data for energy access planning.
- Provide policy and investment insights based on modelling outputs.

1.3 Connection to M300

This report supports the M300 project led by the AFDB and World Bank, in collaboration with various partners, striving to provide electricity access to 300 million people by 2030. It strengthens national capacity for comprehensive, data-driven energy planning, ensuring more efficient and effective electrification strategies.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Modelling Tool Implemented

The Open-Source Spatial Electrification Tool (OnSSET) was used for scenario modelling. OnSSET enables spatial least-cost analysis to determine the most economically viable technology option (grid, mini-grid, or standalone) per settlement. OnSSET is supported by a script run through an anaconda environment and python code/Jupyter notebook. OnSSET's Python script was calibrated using sensitivity analyses for PV cost reductions and grid-connection limits to validate robustness.

2.2 Data Sources

- **Demographics:** Uganda Bureau of Statistics (UBOS) – Population Census 2024.
- **Grid infrastructure:** UETCL, REA mapping data. – Energy GIS
- **Demand profiles:** Household sizes (Rural: 5, Urban: 4), urbanization at 60% by 2040. - UBOS
- **Technology costs:** IEA, IRENA, GET.transform databases (Default inputs)
- **GIS Base Maps:** OpenStreetMap, QGIS land cover layers.
- **Other data** – Roads, settlements, humdata, energydata info, diva maps etc
- **Solar PV & Wind Data** – ESMAP Maps

2.3 Data Preparation

Raw data was cleaned, harmonized, and reprojected using QGIS using the coordinate system WGS 84 (EPSG:4326). Population raster datasets were aggregated by village clusters, matched with demand profiles, and overlaid with grid infrastructure data. Anaconda and Python libraries were used to create the right environment and scenario was run with a python scrip.

2.4 Assumptions & National challenges

- Start year:2024
- Start year Population: 2040
- Target Year: 2040.
- Target access rate: 100%
- Population: 61 million.
- Urbanization: 60%.
- Household Size: Rural (5), Urban (4).
- Electricity Tier Goals: Rural (Tier 2), Urban (Tier 3+)
- Falling prices of PV technology and tax exemptions on PV

2.5 Scenarios Modelled

2.5.1 Scenario 1: Ideal Grid Scenario

This scenario is based on the assumption that conditions are ideal and the government has all the funds for electrification available. The scenario applied automatic OnSSET parameters for least cost electrification technology with population input values as: Start year of 2024 with calibrated data at 25% access & end year 100% access by 2040, Population2040 at 61 million, urban ratio – 60%, Urban household 4 and rural household 5, no limit on grid connections.

2.5.2 Scenario 2: Off-grid Priority Scenario

The second scenario was developed based on challenges cited in the background of this report and results from the ideal Grid Scenario indicating a high annual investment requirement. Scenario 2 took into account the following factors;

- High reliance on off-grid solar: National statistics indicate that most settlements are rural, with over 50% of households electrified through solar home systems (SHS).
- Government support for solar: Solar home systems are subsidized through tax exemptions, encouraging uptake.
- Financing gap: The electrification sector has historically received about \$285 million annually—well below the estimated \$640 million required to meet universal access targets.
- Favorable PV market trends: The international cost of photovoltaic (PV) equipment continues to decline, coupled with rapid technological advancements.

Scenario 2 simulation inputs were based on an ideal scenario for all population factors with the following inputs adjusted.

- Limited annual grid connections – maximum 300,000 grid connections per year
- Lower PV costs with more electrification via SHS (30% reduction) and mini-grids (10%)
- Lower tier for rural areas (2)

3.0 Results

3.1 Scenario 1 – Ideal Scenario

In scenario 1 – Ideal scenario, the results were 100% electrification, with the population electrified with technologies below.

- Grid densification (56.4%)
- Grid extension (22.5%)
- Solar PV (20.8%)
- Minigrids (0.3%).
- Total investment required is \$9.6 billion (approximately \$641 million per year)

The figures below show the graphs based on summaries from the simulation. Figure 1 shows the share of investment by technology.

Figure 1: Ideal scenario – Share of Investment required by technology

Figure 2, shows percentage of investment against the population electrified and technology

Figure 2: Technology by population vs % investment requirement

Figure 3 provides a visualization of the ideal scenario in QGIS, showing how technologies and MV lines are distributed across the country.

Figure 3: Ideal scenario - QGIS Visualization

Of the \$9.6 billion investment required for the ideal scenario;

- Grid densification taking up 54.5% of the investment and adding 41% new connections
- Grid extension taking 33.1% of investment and adding 29.1% new connection
- SHS requires 11.8% investment and electrified 28.1% new connections
- PV Minigrids taking up 0.3% of the investment and 0.39% new connections

3.2 Scenario 2– Offgrid Scenario

In this scenario, the results for electrification were;

- Grid densification (56.4%)
- Grid extension (2%)
- Solar PV (26%)
- Minigrids (14%)
- Total investment required was \$9.2 billion (approximately \$615 million per year)

It is important to note that grid densification investment did not change from the ideal scenario but grid intensification significantly reduced in favour of offgrid solutions. Figure 4 below shows the total investment required for scenario 2.

Figure 4: Offgrid scenario - Investment by technology

Figure 5 below shows the population electrified, the rate of investment against each of the technologies. From below, it is observed that offgrid investment for SHS and minigrids increased as well as the total population to be electrified.

Figure 5: Population electrified and % of investment against technology

The offgrid scenario was visualized in QGIS as per the map in figure 6 below;

Figure 6: Visualization of offgrid scenario in QGIS

From this scenario, total investment required is \$9.2 billion. Of the \$9.2 billion investment;

- Grid densification taking up 56.8% of the investment and adding 41.4% new connections
- Grid extension taking 3.1% of investment and adding 2.2% new connections
- SHS requires 26.0% investment and electrified 51.7% new connections
- PV Minigrids taking up 14.1% of the investment and 4.65% connections

Overall, the table below summarizes the results of the two scenarios side by side over the duration of the simulation 2024 - 2040.

Technology	Ideal Scenario		Offgrid Scenario	
	Investment (billion \$)	Connections %	Investment (billion \$)	Connections %
Grid Densification	5.2	41.41%	5.2	41.41%
Grid Extension	3.2	29.40%	0.3	2.24%
SHS	1.1	28.80%	2.4	51.70%
PV Minigrid	0.1	0.39%	1.3	4.65%
	9.6		9.2	

4.0 Discussion & Recommendation

Based on the two scenarios, we evaluated the annual electrification budget—currently assumed to be fully allocated to grid electrification—against future needs, as shown in the table below. The findings were as follows;

- The Ideal Scenario requires that government make an annual investment of \$571 million, more than double the current budget of \$285 million, which may be fiscally unrealistic.
- Under the Off-grid Scenario, the government would need to mobilize \$357 million annually for grid-related investments— only \$72 million more than the current allocation.
- The Off-grid Scenario also enables the government to leverage \$258 million in private capital annually (through solar home systems and mini-grids), making universal electrification more financially feasible.

Scenario	Annual investment (million \$)	% of Grid investment	Grid budget requirement	Out of budget grid investment	Private Capital
Baseline (2024 spending)	285	100%	285	-	-
Ideal Scenario (2040)	641	89%	571	286	70
Off-grid Scenario (2040)	615	58%	357	72	258

The baseline spending reflects Uganda's current spending level and is financially sustainable. However, it may not be sufficient to significantly accelerate access unless complemented by targeted strategies.

The ideal scenario spending represents the most ambitious plan but comes with a steep funding gap. Given budget limitations and slow progress from past grid expansion efforts, it is likely unrealistic in the short to medium term without substantial external financing. While requiring

modestly more funding, this approach allows for wider access by leveraging private investment in off-grid technologies. It balances cost and impact, making it a pragmatic and scalable solution for expanding energy access.

Uganda should therefore **adopt the off-grid scenario** as its core electrification strategy. This pathway:

- Aligns closely with current trends where over half of the population is connected via solar.
- Aligns with budgetary constraints while achieving national goals.
- Enables faster and more flexible energy access through off-grid private sector participation.
- Preserves grid investments through selective extension and intensification only where essential.
- Leverages private sector funds from offgrid service providers and investors.
- Mirrors regional trends e.g. popularity of SHS systems in the region. Countries like Kenya, Tanzania and Rwanda have significant part of their electrification coming from SHS.

4.1 Limitations

- Cost data uncertainties for remote areas.
- Lack of detailed load profiles.
- Static assumptions on household demand and not taking into account commercial and industrial demand. Static demand assumptions could be addressed by incorporating UBOS's future household surveys.
- Climate adaptation measures not included.

5.0 Conclusion & Future Work

This study demonstrates that Uganda can achieve universal electricity access by 2040 through an off-grid led strategy that aligns with national development goals and fiscal limitations. OnSSET modelling shows that decentralization not only reduces costs but also accelerates service delivery. Institutional adoption of tools like OnSSET and regular data updates are critical. Policies must now pivot toward flexibility, inclusion of private actors, and coordinated planning across sectors.

For future work, the government could explore additional scenarios that maximize electrification and productivity and balance national budgetary targets and goals. Some of these are hybrid scenario – Grid&Offgrid; explore more cost reduction or incremental scenarios and other factors within the OnSSET. Productive-Use-Electrification scenario – prioritize areas of productivity, add agricultural data, tourism, and other productive clusters. Climate resilient electrification scenario – integrate climate resilience data and use it to guide electrification choices (overlay climate and electrification maps. Public facilities electrification scenario – one that prioritizes access to government facilities. Demand aggregation scenario – focus on areas with high demand with gradual spillover into rural areas. Reverse modelling –focus on realities of budgetary allocations to derive the best possible electrification scenario. Scenarios allowing unelectrified populations or shorter period e.g. 2030

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7.0 Appendices

Scenario – CSV files

scenario_1_Summari
es.csv

scenario_1_Variables.
csv

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